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**Estimation of N₂O emissions from wastewater characteristics in
constructed wetlands**

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1 **Highlights**

- 2 • An empirical model was developed relating N₂O EFs and wastewater characteristics
- 3 • The application of the model to small settlements estimated an N₂O EF of 0.94%
- 4 • Specific emission of N₂O from CWs was 60.82 mg N₂O per day and person equivalent
- 5 • Between CWs and conventional WWTPs, lower N₂O emissions are expected to CWs
- 6 • The lowest N₂O EF in CWs is expected for high strength municipal wastewater

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1 **Abstract**

2 Conventional wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) contribute significantly to the
3 nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions. On the other hand, the contribution of constructed
4 wetlands (CWs) to N₂O emissions is not clear. In this study, a literature review was
5 initially conducted to study the factors that are correlated with N₂O emissions from these
6 systems. Afterwards, a statistical formula was developed using the metaregression method
7 for estimating N₂O emission factors (EFs) from CWs. This formula related EFs with
8 influent wastewater characteristics (chemical oxygen demand-COD, total nitrogen-TN,
9 COD/TN) and was applied to 56 small Greek settlements for predicting N₂O emissions in
10 an alternate scenario where CWs technology would be applied instead of conventional
11 WWTPs. The estimated N₂O EFs for the alternate scenario at these settlements ranged
12 between 0.21% and 3.20% (as N₂O/TN influent load), while the average value was equal
13 to 0.94%. The specific N₂O emission was estimated to 60.82 mg N₂O per day and person
14 equivalent. The application of different scenarios with wastewater of different strength
15 showed that the lowest N₂O EF in CWs is expected for wastewater with high initial COD
16 and TN concentrations. To compare N₂O emissions from CWs and conventional WWTPs,
17 the Ordinary Least Squares multiple regression method was also applied to develop a
18 general statistical equation that relates N₂O EFs from conventional WWTPs with
19 wastewater characteristics. According to the results, the estimated N₂O emissions from
20 the Greek settlements for conventional wastewater treatment are larger for 77% of the
21 studied cases compared to emissions found if CW technology had been applied instead.

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23 **Keywords:** GHGs, nitrous oxide, wastewater treatment, constructed wetlands, N₂O
24 emission factor

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1. Introduction

Nitrous oxide (N_2O) is an important greenhouse gas with a global warming potential 298 times higher than (carbon dioxide) CO_2 on a 100 year horizon [1]. It contributes to stratospheric ozone depletion [2] and it accounts for 6.2% of the total anthropogenic GHG emissions [3]. Agriculture, chemical industries and waste management are considered as the main sources of N_2O [4], while biomass, fossil fuel combustion, fertilizer management and the production of adipic and nitric acid contribute to its emissions to the atmosphere [5].

Numerous articles have also pointed out the importance of municipal wastewater treatment for N_2O emissions as well as their contribution to total GHG emissions [3, 6-8]. The main biological processes of N_2O production during wastewater treatment are a) nitrification through the NH_2OH oxidation pathway by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria, b) nitrifier denitrification where nitrite (NO_2^-) is reduced to N_2O by autotrophic ammonia-oxidizing bacteria and c) heterotrophic denitrification where denitrifiers reduce nitrate (NO_3^-) or NO_2^- to N_2 via N_2O . N_2O can also be produced through NH_2OH and NO_2^- abiotic reactions [3]. Most of the published information in the field originates from the operation of conventional wastewater treatment systems. In a recent review article, Vasilaki et al. [8] discussed recent findings from the monitoring of N_2O in full-scale wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) that applied conventional (e.g. activated sludge) or novel (e.g. partial-nitrification-anammox) biological treatment processes in terms of N_2O EFs. According to this review, a wide range of EFs has been reported which seems to be controlled by several factors such as the duration of the monitoring campaign, the configuration of the reactors and the capacity of studied WWTPs.

On the other hand, constructed wetlands (CWs) have been extensively used as alternative wastewater treatment systems for the treatment of wastewater produced in

1 small settlements, due to their lower construction and operational costs, lower energy
2 demand and maintenance requirements [9, 10]. It is not clear yet what the carbon footprint
3 of these systems is and how their N₂O emissions compare to those of conventional
4 WWTPs. To answer these questions, during the last decade several lab-scale, pilot-scale
5 or full-scale surveys with CWs have been conducted applying different sampling
6 strategies and experimental designs, and information on the factors that are correlated
7 with N₂O emissions and the values of EFs in CWs has been reported. Except for the older
8 review papers published by Mander et al. [11] and Mander et al. [12], to the best of our
9 knowledge, this information has not been systematically organized, analyzed and
10 discussed. Furthermore, so far there have not been any attempts to create a general
11 empirical model that relates N₂O EFs in CWs with wastewater characteristics. Such a
12 model could be used for estimating N₂O emissions in an existing CW, as well as for
13 predicting the emissions in case this technology would be applied for wastewater
14 treatment of specific settlements.

15 Based on the above, the main objectives of the current study were to report and
16 discuss the EFs that have been published for N₂O in CWs treating wastewater, and to
17 develop a general statistical equation that relates EFs with wastewater characteristics. To
18 achieve these objectives, a literature review was initially conducted for N₂O emissions by
19 CWs and information for the tested treatment systems, the N₂O EFs, the influent
20 wastewater characteristics (total nitrogen, TN; ammonium nitrogen, NH₄⁺-N; chemical
21 oxygen demand, COD; ratio of COD to TN, COD/TN) and the N₂O flux were recorded.
22 Afterwards, the metaregression method was applied to derive a statistical model relating
23 N₂O EFs and influent characteristics. This equation was subsequently applied using
24 measurements from Greece in order to estimate the expected emissions of N₂O from small
25 settlements (< 10,000 inhabitants) in case that CW technology would be selected instead

1 of the conventional treatment for the produced wastewater treatment. Finally, the
2 predicted N₂O emissions from CWs and conventional wastewater treatment systems were
3 compared and the correlation of influent wastewater strength with emitted N₂O was
4 discussed.

5

6 **2. Materials and Methods**

7 **2.1. Data collection**

8 We retrieved information on N₂O emissions from CWs and the parameters correlated
9 with them from 52 articles published between 1999 and 2021 from the Scopus database,
10 using as keywords ‘N₂O emission’ AND ‘nitrous oxide’ AND ‘CW’ AND ‘artificial
11 wetlands’ (Table S1). To create a statistical model relating N₂O EFs and influent
12 wastewater characteristics, seven (7) of the above articles were used, as important
13 information (e.g. N₂O EF, NH₄⁺-N concentration, COD concentration or TN
14 concentration) was missing from the rest of the articles. The values of N₂O EFs were
15 retrieved for 2 of the 7 articles [13, 14], while for the other 5 studies, they were calculated
16 using Equation 1, as described in Section 2.2.

17 For the estimation of the N₂O emissions from small Greek settlements, data for the
18 served population, the flow rate and the chemical characteristics of raw sewage (COD,
19 total nitrogen, NH₄⁺-N concentrations) were taken from a previous study published by the
20 authors for 56 Greek areas with served population lower than 10,000 person equivalent
21 (PE) [7].

22

23 **2.2. Calculations and Statistical Analysis**

24 The values of N₂O EFs (as % N₂O/TN influent load) were calculated using N₂O flux
25 values and TN influent concentrations according to Equation 1:

1
$$EF_{N_2O} = \frac{J \times S}{TN \times Q} \times 100 \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

2 Where J is the N₂O flux from the studied wetland system (mg/m² d), S is the wetland's
3 surface area (m²), TN is the total nitrogen concentration in influent wastewater (mg/L)
4 and Q is the wastewater flowrate (L/d).

5 Standard deviation (σ) was used as a measure of variation of each N₂O EF estimate
6 and was calculated based on the σ of TN, using error propagation and assuming a constant
7 Q as reported in each study:

8
$$\sigma_{EF} = EF \times \frac{\sigma_{TN}}{TN} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

9 In the literature, N₂O EFs are estimated either as % N₂O-N/TN influent or as %
10 N₂O/TN influent. For comparison purposes, in the present study all N₂O EFs were
11 expressed as % N₂O/TN influent, using Equation 3:

12
$$\%N_2O/TN_{\text{influent}} = (\%N_2O - N/TN_{\text{influent}}) \times \frac{44}{28} \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

13 Where 44/28 is the conversion factor for expressing kg N₂O-N into kg N₂O.

14 We applied a metaregression analysis [15] to derive an empirical model relating the
15 dependent variable N₂O EF (as % N₂O/TN influent) with the wastewater characteristics
16 COD, TN, NH₄⁺-N concentrations and COD/TN ratio as independent variables
17 (moderators). Metaregression is frequently applied on study-level data to take into
18 account both sampling error and between-study heterogeneity, aiming to derive an
19 equation that adequately generalizes the phenomenon under investigation [16].
20 Metaregression initially estimates the between-study heterogeneity (τ^2) and subsequently
21 fits a regression line using weighted least squares, with studies with a smaller standard
22 error having given a higher weight in the overall model. In our model we allowed an
23 intercept since there is evidence that abiotic reactions lead to N₂O production irrespective
24 of our independent variables [17]. The analysis was performed in R [18], using the

1 package metafor [19], and model selection was performed using an exhaustive search
2 procedure, retaining the combination of predictor variables with the highest R^2 .

3 After deriving the empirical model, the EF for each CW of the Greek study areas was
4 estimated and subsequently used to estimate the N_2O emissions (kg/day) using Equation 4:

$$5 \quad N_2O_{\text{emissions}} = \frac{TN \times Q \times EF_{N_2O}}{10^5} \quad (\text{Equation 4})$$

6 Where TN is the total nitrogen concentration in influent wastewater (mg/L) and Q is the
7 wastewater flowrate (m^3/d).

8

9 **Results and discussion**

10 **3.1 Profile of the research papers containing information for N_2O emissions in CWs**

11 An extended literature review was conducted and data was retrieved for N_2O emis-
12 sions in CWs from 52 articles (Table S1). Twenty (20) of them were published between
13 1999 and 2010, while the rest between 2011 and 2021. Almost half of the articles originate
14 from China, 6 from Estonia, 5 from Japan, and the rest from countries of Northern Europe
15 (Sweden, Norway, Germany, Finland, France and Poland), USA and Canada. Limited or
16 irrelevant information is available for the areas of the world with sub-tropical or tropical
17 climates. Regarding the type of studied CW, ten (10) articles provide information for the
18 N_2O emission in free water surface (FWS) CWs, sixteen (16) in vertical flow (VF) CWs
19 and six (6) in subsurface horizontal flow (HSSF) CWs. The rest of the articles refer to dif-
20 ferent combinations of CWs while two of them were review papers.

21 Twenty six (26) of the reviewed studies were conducted in lab-scale systems, eight (8)
22 in pilot-scale, while sixteen (16) articles describe the operation of full-scale systems. The
23 total period of operation for the systems varied from one month (short-term experimental
24 procedure) to 2.5 years (long-term experimental procedure), while there were nine (9)
25 studies where this information was not reported. Concerning the procedure that was fol-

1 lowed for the monitoring of N₂O emissions, the closed chamber technique was mainly ap-
2 plied (86% of studies) for the collection of gas samples, while the N₂O analysis was con-
3 ducted in most of the cases using gas chromatography with an electron capture detector
4 (GC-ECD). The average temperature varied from 14.7 °C to 28.5 °C in lab-scale experi-
5 ments, from 7.6 °C to 17 °C in pilot-scale experiments and from 1 °C to 17.1 °C in full-
6 scale systems. Synthetic wastewater was used in most of the studies, while municipal
7 wastewater [13, 20-25], swine wastewater [14, 26-29], agricultural runoff water [30-31],
8 stormwater [32] and nitrate dominated river water [33] have also been tested.

10 **3.2 Parameters correlated with N₂O emission factors (EFs) in CW systems**

11 N₂O is related to nitrification and denitrification processes. During nitrification am-
12 monium nitrogen (NH₄⁺-N) is transformed to nitrate nitrogen (NO₃⁻-N), which is elimi-
13 nated by denitrification [34], while nitrite nitrogen (NO₂⁻-N) is an intermediate product of
14 nitrification and denitrification processes [35]. N₂O is an intermediate product of incom-
15 plete nitrification and denitrification [34].

16 The reported N₂O emissions from the CWs treating wastewater present important vari-
17 ations and seem to be correlated with several factors such as the nitrogen and carbon load
18 [14, 36], the influent ratio of C to N [10, 34, 35], the plant cover species [10, 37-38], the
19 dissolved oxygen concentration [10, 35, 39], the pH and the temperature [35, 39], the cli-
20 mate and seasonal variations [10, 38], the wastewater flow and the CW age [40], the type
21 of the CW system [39], the applied hydraulic residence time, HRT [10, 35], the feeding
22 strategy [41], the aeration type [42-43], the water table fluctuations [44] and the used sub-
23 strate materials [45-47].

24 An overview of the different physical or operational factors that have been studied in
25 lab-scale, pilot-scale and full-scale CW systems is presented in Table S1. In this table in-

1 formation is also provided for the location of each study, the methodology that was ap-
2 plied for measuring N₂O, and the operational conditions (temperature, HRT, type of
3 wastewater etc). In the cases where N₂O EFs had not been calculated or reported in the
4 initial articles, their values (as % N₂O-N/TN influent) were obtained from Mander et al.
5 [12] or they were calculated using Equation 1. For the articles where one of the necessary
6 parameters of Equation 1 was missing (e.g. N₂O flux, wastewater flowrate or wetland sur-
7 face area), N₂O EFs were not calculated and these articles were used only for studying the
8 parameters that are correlated with N₂O EFs.

9 According to the published results, there is a wide range of variation of the N₂O EFs
10 (%N₂O/TN influent). In lab-scale studies, the N₂O EFs ranged from <0.01% to 2.05%
11 (0.06-2.05% in free water surface (FWS) CWs, <0.01-0.27% in vertical subsurface
12 (VSSF) CWs, 0.07-2.00% in subsurface (SSF) CWs), in pilot-scale studies from 0.07% to
13 1.51% (0.08-1.51% in FCWs, 0.07-0.15% in VSSF CWs, 0.36% in horizontal subsurface
14 (HSSF) CWs) and in full-scale systems from <0.01% to 4.73% (<0.01-0.46% in FWS
15 CWs, 0.02-0.68% in VSSF CWs, 0.06-4.73% in HSSF CWs). In the following
16 paragraphs, the role of different factors on EF values is discussed in brief.

17 TN concentration is considered as an influencing factor on N₂O emissions, due to the
18 positive relationship between N₂O emissions and NO₃⁻-N concentration. Specifically, low
19 values of TN mean low values of NO₃⁻-N concentration leading to the restraint of
20 denitrification and low N₂O emissions, while high values of TN concentration may lead to
21 anaerobic conditions that enhance complete denitrification and elimination of NO₃⁻-N,
22 resulting to lower N₂O emissions [14]. Furthermore, a positive relationship between N₂O
23 emissions and NO₂⁻-N concentration was observed at the study of Wu et al. [35], which is
24 probably ascribed to chemo-denitrification process due to NO₂⁻-N accumulation, leading
25 to N₂ and N₂O or to the toxic influence of NO₂⁻-N on denitrification.

1 COD concentration is correlated with N₂O emissions as it has a significant effect on
2 the denitrification process [36]. Low concentrations of available organic carbon inhibit
3 denitrification [43], while the existence of adequate carbon results to complete
4 denitrification and production of N₂ [12].

5 COD/TN is a crucial parameter correlated with N₂O emissions, as it affects both
6 nitrification and denitrification processes [48]. The role of this parameter has so far been
7 studied in lab-scale experiments and contradictory results have been reported [34, 35, 48].
8 Specifically, in experiments with SF CWs, Li et al. [48] applied different COD/TN values
9 (0.11, 1.13, 2.53, 5.38, and 10.98) and N₂O EF values equal to 1.13% and 2.05% for
10 COD/TN ratio of 1.13 and 10.98, respectively were estimated. Furthermore, COD/TN
11 values equal to 0.09, 2.23, 5.63, 12.09 and 23 were tested by Wu et al. [35] in lab-scale
12 experiments with FWS CWs and the minimum N₂O EF value was observed for COD/TN
13 ratio of 23 and it was equal to 0.06%. Li et al. [36] performed lab-scale experiments in
14 subsurface wastewater infiltration systems (SWISs) using different COD concentrations
15 and the N₂O EF was estimated to be 2% for COD concentration of 280 mg/L and
16 COD/TN equal to 15.56. In a lab-scale study conducted with SSF CWs, Lyu et al. [34]
17 used COD/TN ratio of 0, 4, 7, 10, 20; the minimum value of EF (0.07%) was observed for
18 COD/TN ratio of 7 when sodium acetate was used as carbon source, while EF was much
19 higher (0.34%) when glucose was used as substrate. This is mainly ascribed to the fact
20 that the microbial community as well as the denitrification are also affected by the
21 available carbon source [34].

22 The seasonal variations of N₂O emissions have been studied in many studies [10, 13,
23 24, 38, 49, 50]. N₂O emissions present higher values in summer [50, 51] or autumn [22]
24 as low temperatures have negative effects to the denitrification and nitrification processes
25 [51]. It is important to underline that in most of the studies, N₂O EFs are based on data

1 from one year or a single vegetation period. As a result, no clear conclusions can be
2 drawn for the role of seasonality on N₂O EFs.

3 Concerning the effect of vegetation on N₂O EF, the type of plant has a great influence
4 on the transportation of organics and the microbial community of ammonia-oxidizing
5 bacteria (AOB) [52]. For the non-vegetated control, several researches have observed the
6 lowest values of EFs in VSSF systems [50-52], while high values have been reported for
7 HSSF CWs [51]. According to Sjøvik et al. [51], the lowest values of EF at non-vegetated
8 VSSF control may be ascribed to the fact that the plants enhance microbial community,
9 while they also affect the transportation of organics and enhance nitrification via
10 oxygenation. For the role of different plants on N₂O EFs, Wang et al. [52] used lab-scale
11 VSSF and the lowest EF value (0.05%) were observed with *Phragmites australis* and
12 *Zizania latifolia*, whereas the highest value (0.09%) with *Phragmites australis* and *Typha*
13 *latifolia*. However, it should be noted that contradictory results have been reported in
14 different studies for the same type of vegetation in VSSF CWs. For instance, Teiter and
15 Mander [22] reported N₂O EF equal to 0.03% for *Phragmites australis* in full-scale VSSF
16 while Filali et al. [13] calculated a value of 0.68% for full-scale VSSF systems planted
17 with the same species. It is observed that the different studies examining the effect of
18 different plant species on N₂O EFs often report contradictory results and more research is
19 needed in parallel experiments to clarify the role of each plant species on N₂O EF.

20 The type of CW system is another important factor which can potentially be correlated
21 with N₂O EFs. In the current literature several studies have reported that the vertical flow
22 wetlands emit more N₂O than the horizontal flow wetlands [21, 23, 25, 53] and the free
23 water surface wetlands [23, 51, 54] because of the aerobic conditions which affect the
24 nitrification and the denitrification [51]. On the contrary, Van der Zaag et al. [55]
25 observed higher values at surface (SF) CWs than SSF CWs. Sjøvik et al. [51] reported that

1 overland and groundwater flow (OGF) wetlands had the lowest emission rates both during
2 winter and summer compared to the other types of CWs while Mander et al. [25]
3 observed no remarkable variation on N₂O emissions between the studied CW systems.
4 Concerning N₂O EFs, lower values have been reported for vertical flow CWs than the
5 other types of CW [22, 51, 54], even though Gui et al. [23] observed lower values in free
6 water surface wetlands than vertical flow wetlands. Further studies on the correlation of
7 the type of CW system with N₂O EFs are required.

8 Another parameter that has been studied as it seems to be correlated with N₂O EFs is
9 the water level in the CW. Mander et al. [44] reported EFs equal to 0.09% and 0.30% at
10 high and low water level, respectively, in a full-scale HSSF CW.

11 Finally, the effect of substrate materials on N₂O emission was studied during the last
12 years. Cheng et al. [45] observed that Mn oxides lead to higher removal efficiency of TN
13 and lower N₂O emissions than Fe oxides at vertical subsurface-flow CWs, due to their
14 effect on microbial community. In addition, Xu et al. [46] reported that Mn ore presented
15 the highest TN removal efficiency and simultaneously low N₂O emissions as Mn oxide
16 enhance microbial processes acting as an electron acceptor. In the same study, walnut
17 shell lead to the lowest N₂O emissions than the other studied substrates as it enhanced
18 both nitrification via oxygenation and denitrification as a carbon source. Finally, Ji et al.
19 [47] reported that biochar amended CWs presented lower N₂O emissions and better N₂O
20 removal performance comparing to ceramsite CWs.

21

22 **3.3 Developing an empirical equation relating N₂O emission factors (EFs) with** 23 **wastewater characteristics**

24 Taking into account the results of the aforementioned review and the complex role of
25 different factors on N₂O EFs in CWs, we tried to develop a general simplified statistical

1 model that relates EFs with wastewater characteristics. For this reason, we used seven (7)
2 of the reviewed articles (Table S2) that contained all the necessary data for the method
3 development; namely: EFs from CWs and concentrations of COD, TN and $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ in the
4 influent wastewater. As there was a strong collinearity between TN and $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$, the latter
5 term was not used in the development of the linear model, to avoid sensitivity in the
6 estimated coefficients and weakening of the statistical power of the equation. All possible
7 elimination combinations were evaluated for the remaining three independent quantities
8 (TN, COD, COD/TN). Nevertheless, the model with the largest R^2 is the one containing
9 all remaining three predictor variables:

$$10 \quad \text{EF} = 0.2536 + 0.0070 \times \text{TN} - 0.0029 \times \text{COD} + 0.1729 \times \frac{\text{COD}}{\text{TN}} \quad (\text{Equation 5})$$

11 with a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) equal to 0.435. The amount of residual
12 heterogeneity $\tau^2 = 0.1667$ indicated that almost 50% ($R^2 = 0.496$) of the total amount of
13 heterogeneity can be accounted for by including the three moderators in the model.

14 This is the first time that an empirical formula is developed for describing the relation
15 between wastewater characteristics and N_2O EFs in CWs. According to this equation, it
16 seems that the EF is correlated with TN and COD concentrations as well as by the ratio of
17 COD to TN. Equation 5 also allows the prediction of N_2O emissions by CWs in case that
18 wastewater characteristics are available. Even though no equations predicting N_2O EFs in
19 CWs are available in the literature, specific coefficients are commonly used for the
20 conventional wastewater treatment systems [56]. For instance, a N_2O EF value of 0.005
21 kg $\text{N}_2\text{O-N/kg}$ effluent N has been reported by IPCC [57], while a N_2O EF of 0.016 kg
22 $\text{N}_2\text{O-N/kg}$ influent N was recently reported [58].

23

24 **3.4 Estimation of N_2O emissions from small Greek settlements served by CWs**

1 To estimate the N₂O emissions from small Greek settlements with PE less than 10,000
2 in the alternate scenario of CW technology adoption for wastewater treatment, the present
3 statistical model was applied for 56 Greek settlements where influent wastewater
4 characteristics were available [7]. EFs for each settlement were calculated using Equation
5 5. Afterwards, Equation 4 was used to estimate the relevant N₂O emissions from each
6 settlement.

7 Although all Greek settlements studied in the present work had low population ranging
8 between 1,500 and 9,955 inhabitants, there were important differences on COD (31 to 941
9 mg/L) and TN concentrations (2 to 169 mg/L) of their influent wastewater (Table S3). No
10 important correlation was observed between the concentrations of pollutants and the
11 number of inhabitants (Figures S1, S2) indicating that these differences are probably due
12 to the type of sewerage system used in each case (separate, combined) as well as to the
13 nature of each settlement (domestic region, touristic region, existence of agro-industries in
14 the area). The average COD concentration for the 56 small Greek settlements was $412 \pm$
15 200 mg/L (Table 1), and it was not statistically different from the average COD
16 concentration of influent wastewater reported for 220 Greek WWTPs serving population
17 up to 3,500,000 inhabitants (528 ± 228 mg/L) [7].

18 Concerning the estimated N₂O EFs in the 56 studied small settlements, as it is shown
19 in Table 1, their values varied from 0.21% to 3.20%, while the average value was equal to
20 0.94% (as N₂O/TN influent load). In detail, the N₂O EF was lower than 0.5% for 21% of
21 the studied areas (12 out of 56), varied from 0.5% to 1% for 54% of the cases (30 out of
22 56) and it ranged between 1% and 3.20% for the rest (Table S3). With few exceptions,
23 values of N₂O EFs between 0.21% and 1.24% (average N₂O EF = 0.70%) were observed
24 for COD/TN ranging between 2.47 and 9.3, while N₂O EFs higher than 1% were
25 estimated for COD/TN > 9.3 (average N₂O EF = 1.58%) (Figure 1).

1 The calculation of the expected daily N₂O emissions at the studied settlements showed
2 N₂O emissions lower than 0.20 kg/d for 22 CWs, between 0.20 and 0.40 kg/d for 18 CWs,
3 between 0.40 and 0.60 kg/d for 10 CWs and up to 1.25 kg/day for 6 CWs (Table S3).
4 Finally, calculation of the per capita N₂O emissions from the CWs showed that the
5 specific emissions varied significantly between 3.63 and 193.53 mg N₂O per day and PE,
6 while the average value was equal to 60.82 mg N₂O per day and PE (Table 1, Table S3).

7

8 **3.5. Comparing N₂O emissions from CWs and conventional WWTPs**

9 So far, no comparisons between N₂O emissions from CWs and conventional
10 wastewater treatment systems are available in the literature. To perform one such
11 comparison, we developed a general statistical equation that relates N₂O EFs from
12 conventional WWTPs with wastewater characteristics (TN concentration, NH₄⁺-N
13 concentration, COD concentration and COD/TN ratio). For this reason, we used data from
14 seventeen (17) articles studying N₂O emissions in activated sludge systems (Table S4)
15 and we applied the Ordinary Least Squares multiple regression method, to find the
16 statistical equation relating the dependent variable N₂O EF (as % N₂O/TN influent)
17 linearly with the wastewater characteristics COD, TN, NH₄⁺-N concentrations and
18 COD/TN as independent variables. The analysis was performed in Python (using the
19 packages pandas and NumPy) and model selection was performed using an exhaustive
20 search procedure, retaining the combination of predictor variables with the lowest Akaike
21 Information Criterion (AIC) value. We found that the statistical model with the largest
22 adjusted R², and the lowest Akaike and Bayesian Information Criteria, has as a single
23 independent variable, the ratio COD/TN:

$$24 \quad EF = 0.14 \times \frac{COD}{TN} \quad (\% \text{ N}_2\text{O/TN influent}) \quad (\text{Equation 6})$$

25 (R squared 30% and adjusted R squared 26%)

1 The estimated N₂O emissions (kg/day) and specific N₂O emissions (mg/ day PE) from
2 the 56 Greek settlements with less than 10,000 PE for conventional wastewater treatment
3 are larger for 77% of the studied cases compared to emissions found if CW technology
4 had been applied instead (Figure 2, Figure S3). For the conventional WWTPs, the average
5 N₂O emission was 0.52 ± 0.59 kg/d and the average specific emission was 99.02 ± 85.51
6 mg /day PE while the relevant values for the CWs were 0.32 ± 0.26 kg/d and $60.82 \pm$
7 40.22 mg / day PE, respectively. For the conventional WWTPs the total N₂O emission
8 was 29.19 kg/d, at a percentage of 65% higher than the relevant value for the CWs which
9 was 17.65 kg/d.

10 To investigate the correlation of influent wastewater strength with N₂O EFs from CWs
11 and conventional WWTPs, five scenarios were tested as summarised in Table 2.
12 Equations 5 and 6 were applied for N₂O EFs estimation from CWs and conventional
13 WWTPs, respectively, for different wastewater characteristics (Scenario 1: low strength
14 wastewater (COD = 150 mg/L, TN = 20 mg/L), Scenario 2: medium strength wastewater
15 (COD = 400 mg/L, TN = 40 mg/L), Scenario 3: high strength wastewater (COD = 800
16 mg/L, TN = 70 mg/L), Scenario 4: (COD = 800 mg/L, TN = 20 mg/L), Scenario 5: (COD
17 = 400 mg/L, TN = 90 mg/L). According to Table 2, N₂O EFs present lower values for
18 CWs in all of the studied scenarios, except Scenario 1 (low COD-low TN) where N₂O
19 EFs are almost the same for both treatment systems. N₂O EFs in CWs are reduced from
20 low to high strength wastewater, while an opposite trend is observed for the conventional
21 WWTPs. Furthermore, CWs present a much lower value of EF compared to the
22 conventional systems for the high strength wastewater (Table 2). It is remarkable that the
23 highest values of N₂O EFs for both treatment systems are observed in case of high COD
24 and low TN concentrations (Scenario 4), while on the contrary they present low values at
25 conditions of low COD and high TN concentrations (Scenario 5). However, the lowest

1 N₂O EF in CWs is expected for wastewater with high initial COD and TN concentrations.
2 As mentioned before, this is the first time that a statistical formula is developed for
3 describing the relation between N₂O EFs in CWs and wastewater characteristics. Further
4 research is needed to validate this model measuring the N₂O emissions from CWs treating
5 different types of wastewater.

6

7 **4. Conclusions**

8 The literature review showed that N₂O emissions from CWs are correlated with
9 several operational and environmental parameters, while a wide range of EFs has been
10 reported ranging between 0.001% and 4.73%. The empirical model that was developed in
11 this study related N₂O EF from CWs with influent wastewater characteristics (COD
12 concentration, TN concentration, ratio of COD to TN). The application of this model to
13 56 Greek areas with population less than 10,000 inhabitants allowed the prediction of EFs
14 in these settlements and showed that the specific N₂O emission from CWs would be equal
15 to 60.82 mg per day and person equivalent. Comparison of the estimated N₂O emissions
16 from CWs and conventional wastewater treatment systems showed that conventional
17 systems would emit higher amounts of N₂O for 77% of the studied cases. For the
18 conventional WWTPs, the average N₂O emission was estimated to 0.52 ± 0.59 kg/d while
19 the relevant value for the CWs was 0.32 ± 0.26 kg/d. N₂O EFs in CWs are expected to be
20 lower when high strength wastewater are treated.

21

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Figure 1. Estimated N₂O emission factors (EFs) in CWs and COD/TN ratio for the studied Greek settlements

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3 **Figure 2.** Comparison of N₂O emissions (as kg/d) in 56 Greek settlements with PE<10000 for the case that the wastewater are treated via CWs

4 (equation 5) or using conventional WWTPs (equation 6).

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1 **Table 1.** N₂O emission factors (EFs) and predicted N₂O emissions from the CWs of the 56 studied Greek settlements with PE<10,000.

2 Values are also reported for the wastewater characteristics of these systems as mean, standard deviation, median, min and max.

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	PE	Flow rate (m³/day)	Influent COD (mg/L)	Influent TN (mg/L)	Influent COD/TN	EF (%TN Influent load)	TN (kg/d)	N₂O emissions (kg/d)	Specific N₂O emissions (mg/day PE)
Mean	5334	893	412	52	8.79	0.94	48.60	0.32	60.82
sd	2543	704	200	29	4.18	0.61	66.30	0.26	40.22
Median	4925	790	412	49	7.77	0.81	30.47	0.24	52.94
min	1500	55	31	2	2.47	0.21	2.04	0.02	3.63
max	9955	4410	941	169	26.16	3.20	447.10	1.25	193.53

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- 1 **Table 2.** Effect of wastewater strength on predicted N₂O emission factors (EFs) from
- 2 CWs and conventional WWTPs

Scenarios	COD (mg/L)	TN (mg/L)	COD/TN	EF by CWs (% N₂O/TN)	EF by conventional WWTPs (% (N₂O/TN)
Scenario 1: Low strength WW	150	20	7.50	1.26	1.05
Scenario 2 : Medium strength WW	400	40	10.00	1.10	1.40
Scenario 3 : High strength WW	800	70	11.43	0.40	1.60
Scenario 4:	800	20	40.00	4.99	5.60
Scenario 5 :	400	90	4.44	0.49	0.62

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